

University Students' Attitude towards the Use of Botox in Cosmetic Surgeries

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ABSTRACT

Background: Patients seek cosmetic surgery in order to enhance their appearance. It is a type of surgery that uses surgical expertise to correct or improve body imperfections.

Objective: To assess the University students' attitude towards the use of Botox in Cosmetic Surgeries

Methods: a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out at the University of Mosul in the Nineveh Governorate between January 1, 2024, and January 3, 2024. Chance A multi-stage sample was chosen for this investigation. 100 students make up the sample of students at Mosul University. They were split up into four colleges: science, medicine, engineering, and hospitality. A specific consent form was used to obtain the subject's consent to participate in the study.

Results: The results of this study indicate that the majority of the sample consisted of 100 students, that 51% of the sample was between the ages of 18 and 23, that the percentage of the sample that was single was higher than the percentage of married individuals (71%), that 78% of the sample lived in an urban area, and that the sample was distributed among medical, engineering, humanities, and scientific colleges.

Conclusion: The results of this study showed that university students' attitudes and perceptions about plastic surgery were reasonable and moderate, and that the media is a valuable source of information.

KEYWORDS: University students, attitude, Botox, Cosmetic Surgeries.

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INTRODUCTION

Humans are self-improvers by nature. Humans have always sought self-fulfillment through enhancing beauty. Cosmetic procedures kept expanding in order to satisfy this demand ⁽¹⁾. Both surgical and non-surgical procedures are referred to as cosmetic procedures ⁽²⁾. Non-surgical procedures include procedures like laser skin resurfacing, chemical peels, filler, and botulinum toxin injections, as well as vein and laser hair removal ⁽³⁾. Plastic surgery is divided into two subspecialties: reconstructive and cosmetic surgery ⁽⁴⁾. Patients seek cosmetic surgery in order to enhance their appearance. It is a type of surgery that uses surgical expertise to correct or improve body imperfections. Any part of the head, neck, or body can undergo cosmetic surgery, which includes a variety of operations like liposuction, surgical facelifts, rhinoplasty (nose surgery), abdominoplasty (tummy tuck), and breast augmentation ⁽⁵⁾. Reconstructive surgery treats pathological conditions, whether they are morphological or functional, and is not the same as cosmetic

surgery. Plastic reconstructive surgery is a subspecialty of surgery that focuses on correcting facial and body defects resulting from birth disorders, trauma, burns, and diseases. Its primary goal is to restore function to affected body parts and is primarily reconstructive ⁽⁶⁾. Cosmetic surgery has become less common in recent years, as more patients are choosing non-invasive alternatives ⁽⁷⁾. A number of epidemiological variables, social networks, and psychological traits including self-esteem, body image, and other personality traits, as well as other particular psychopathologies are linked to interest in cosmetic surgery. These elements could either favorably or unfavorably influence their desire to look for and have a cosmetic procedure done ⁽⁸⁾. Cosmetic procedures are becoming more and more common in our society, with both surgical and non-surgical procedures performed on a yearly basis. The International Society of Plastic Surgery recently released statistics showing that approximately 20 million cosmetic procedures were carried out globally in 2017. The rising number of cosmetic procedures performed makes this

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a topic worth thinking about, and there is good reason to investigate and ascertain the causes of the growing propensity for these operations. Although numerous studies on surgical and non-surgical procedures have been carried out in Iraqi cities and regions, Mosul City has never been the subject of a prior study. This study aims to highlight and concentrate on a governorate rather than cities and regions.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

A descriptive study carried out at the University of Mosul in the Nineveh Governorate between February 2, 2024, and January 3, 2024. The Nineveh Governorate was the site of the current investigation. It is a northern Iraqi governorate, with Mosul serving as its capital. The second-biggest city in Iraq, Mosul is situated 465 kilometers north of Baghdad. A sample of University of Mosul students was gathered. The University of Mosul conducted the study from February 2, 2024, to January 3, 2024, over a period of one month. For this investigation, probability (multi-stage sample) was chosen. 100 students make up the sample of students at Mosul University. A specific consent form was used to obtain the subject's consent to participate in the study. Four groups: scientific, medical, humanitarian, and engineering. Each of them took roughly fifteen to twenty minutes to finish the

interview and respond to the questionnaire, which was conducted in order to fill it out with the University of Mosul included. A questionnaire was used to gather information and gauge university students' opinions regarding the use of Botox in cosmetic surgeries. The three components that made up the study's instruments were as follows: Part One covers demographic traits such as age, kind of college, marital status, place of residence, income, and whether or not you've had plastic surgery. Part Two: source of information related to the University students' attitude towards the use of Botox in Cosmetic Surgeries. There were seven choices in all. Section Three: This third instrument evaluates university students' perspectives on Botox use in cosmetic surgeries. There were twenty-one multiple-choice questions with three possible answers—agree, disagree, and neutral. The statistical findings were examined using version 26 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). A descriptive methodology was utilized. The demographic description characteristics of the students are computed using percentages and frequencies. The data values were estimated using the means and standard deviation (\pm SD). Utilizing test-retest Pearson coefficient correlation to assess the dependability of the study instruments⁽⁹⁻⁵⁶⁾.

RESULTS

Table (1): Distribution of Demographical Characteristics of sample (100)

Variables	No.	Frequency (%)	Mean +SD
(A):Age			
18 – 23 Years	51	51%	Mean (21.9) SD (1.45)
24 – 29 Years	34	34%	
30- 35 Years	12	12%	
36 Years and more	3	3%	
(B): Type of College			
Medicine	22	22%	
Engineering	13	13%	
Humanity	37	37%	
Scientific	28	28%	
(C):residence			
Urban	78	78%	
Rural	22	22%	
(D):Martial status			
Married	29	29%	
Single	71	%71	
(E):Income			
High	17	17%	
Moderate	80	80%	
Low	3	3 %	
(F): Have you had plastic surgery?			
Yes	31	31%	
No	69	69%	

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Table No. 1 shows that most of the sample participating in the study amounted to 100 students, that most of the study sample was from 18 to 23 years old, at a rate of 51%, and that the sample of single was higher than that of married by (71%),

78% of the sample whose residence was urban, as well the sample was distributed in terms of between colleges of the Medicine, engineering, humanity and scientific.

Table (2): Source of information related to use of Botox in Cosmetic Surgeries

Source	N	%
Internet	41	41%
Friends	19	19%
Relative	18	18%
Improve appearance	10	10%
Celebrities	5	5%
Due to a medical condition	4	4%
Others causes	3	3%

Table(3): Attitude of university students towards the use of Botox in Cosmetic Surgeries.

Attitude level	Frequency	Percent
Poor attitude	22	22%
Moderate attitude	67	67%
Good attitude	11	11%
Total	100	100%

Table No3..A shows that university students' attitude towards the use of Botox in Cosmetic Surgeries was moderate.

DISCUSSION

Both men and women are increasingly having cosmetic surgery performed around the world. Iraq comes in at number 22 out of the top 25 countries in the world for the highest rates of cosmetic procedures, according to a 2013 study by the International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgeons (ISAPS). The study also found that the only Muslim nations with a total of 104,767 and 46,962 surgical procedures performed in 2018 respectively were Saudi Arabia, Iran, Iraq, and Turkey⁽⁵⁷⁾. Iraq has seen a rise in the popularity of cosmetic surgery as a result of the social acceptance of having aesthetic procedures performed and the growing significance placed on beauty standards. To the best of our knowledge, no research has been done on the attitudes of non-medical students toward plastic surgery, not just cosmetic surgery, in the northern region of Iraq. This study set out to determine the prevalence of plastic surgery among female Iraqi university students in Mosul City as well as to evaluate attitudes toward the procedure. Thirty-one percent of 100 Mosul women enrolled in four colleges medicine, engineering, humanities, and sciences had cosmetic surgery. Students most frequently cited the mass media (41%), friends (19%), and other sources of information (19%). A total of 18% mentioned their relatives. additional sources. Our findings concur with those of (58,59), who discovered that study participants initially learned about plastic surgery from the media. It was discovered from the research's findings that university students' attitudes toward plastic surgery were mediocre, which suggests that many of them had opinions and attitudes about the procedure. According to a study⁽⁶⁰⁾ conducted in India among medical professionals, there is limited knowledge of plastic surgery as a specialty. A study

carried out in Hong Kong (2012) revealed that participants were not even willing to marry women who had undergone cosmetic surgery. Some members of the Chinese population believed that the body should not remain intact because it is a guarantee from parents and people like normal things⁽⁵⁸⁾. However, this study supports⁽⁶¹⁾ who noted that most students agreed that cosmetic surgery is common in general and that female medical students' attitudes toward it at Al Riyadh are reasonable. Only 32.7% of respondents in this study said they would support people who have cosmetic surgery, and the majority of them (79.5%) said they would not consent to have cosmetic surgery themselves in the future. According to a Hong Kong-based study, participants are even less likely to have social relationships with people who undergo cosmetic surgery.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study showed that university students' attitudes and perceptions about plastic surgery were reasonable and moderate, and that the media is a valuable source of information.

REFERENCE

1. Rinzler CA. The encyclopedia of cosmetic and plastic surgery. Infobase Publishing; 2010 May 12..
2. Shiffman MA, Di Giuseppe A, editors. Cosmetic surgery: art and techniques. Springer Science & Business Media; 2012 Sep 5.
3. Australian Health Ministers Advisory Council. Cosmetic Medical and Surgical Procedure.2022. A National Framework. Available at:

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<https://www.health.nsw.gov.au/publications/Documents/cosmetic-surgery.pdf>

4. Milothridis P, Pavlidis L, Haidich AB, Panagopoulou E. A systematic review of the factors predicting the interest in cosmetic plastic surgery. *Indian Journal of Plastic Surgery*. 2016 Sep;49(03):397-402.
5. Otene CI, Odonmeta AB, Ebeye OA, Enivwenae AO, Ozoko LE, Ebeigbe PN. Knowledge, attitude and practice of cosmetic surgery among basic science students of a university in Delta state, Nigeria. *J Dent Med Sci*. 2016;15:28-36.
6. Hammadi HA, El-Shereef EA. Study of knowledge, attitude and practices of plastic surgery among females students at faculty of education, Taif University, Saudi Arabia. *Am J Public Health Res*. 2017 Jul 6;5(3):63-9.
7. Aldosari BF, Alkarzae M, Almuhaya R, Aldahri R, Alrashid H. Effect of media on facial plastic surgery in Saudi Arabia. *Cureus*. 2019 Nov 25;11(11).
8. ElHawary H, Hintermayer MA, Alam P, Brunetti VC, Janis JE. Decreasing surgical site infections in plastic surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis of level 1 evidence. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal*. 2021 Jul 1;41(7):NP948-58.
9. Ahmed MM, Younis NM, Dhahir NM, Hussain KN. Acceptance of Covid-19 vaccine among nursing students of Mosul University, Iraq. *Rawal Medical Journal*. 2022 Apr;47(2):254.-
10. Muwfaq Younis N. Efficacy of Health Beliefs Model-Based Intervention in Changing Substance Use Beliefs among Mosul University Students: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Revis Bionatura* 2022; 7 (2) 35.
11. Al-Ghurairi SA, Younis NM, Ahmed MM. Prevalence of weight gain among students of Mosul University, Iraq during quarantine 2020. *Rawal Medical Journal*. 2022 Jul;47(3).
12. Abbas AS, Younis NM. Efficacy of Pender's Health Promotion-based Model on Intervention for Enhancing University of Mosul Hypertensive Employees' Eating Behaviors: A randomized Controlled Trial. *Revis Bionatura*. 2022;7(3):35
13. Ahmed MM, Younis NM, Abdulsalam RR. Assessment of changes in sleep habits in elementary students during covid_19 lockdown. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology & Legal Medicine*. 2022;25(1and2):76-80.
14. Adea MK, Lefta RM, Younis NM. Impact of psychosocial aspect parameters on psoriasis patients' quality of life at outpatient clinic in Al-Dewania City, Iraq. *Rawal Medical Journal*. 2022 Dec 11;47(4):892.-
15. Ibrahim RM, Idrees NH, Younis NM. Epidemiology of leukemia among children in Nineveh Province, Iraq. *Rawal Medical Journal*: 2023 Jan. Vol. 48, (1):137.-
16. Taher AK, Younis NM. Assessment the Effect of a Trans theoretical Model in Improving Behaviors Health Care workers related Electronic Hookah in Mosul City /Iraq. *Rawal Medical Journal*: 2023 Jan. Vol. 48, (1):228.-
17. Mohammad FH, Noori LK, Younis NM. Assessment of Nutritional habits among Mosul University Students regarding breakfast. 2023 Jan. Vol. 48, (1):96.-
18. Younis NM, Ibrahim RM, Idrees NH. Prevalence of snake bite among children in Nineveh Governorate/Iraq: A retrospective study. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology & Legal Medicine*. 2022;25(3and4):169-172.
19. Younis NM, Ahmed MM, Abdulsalam RR. Assessing quality of life in palliative care. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology & Legal Medicine*. 2021;24(3and4):115-8.
20. Ali HA, Abbas FF, Younis NM. Mothers' knowledge and attitudes towards breastfeeding in Thi-Qar City, Iraq. *Rawal Medical Journal*. 2023 May 27;48(2):514.-
21. Bura'a LN, Younis NM. Nurses knowledge regarding to phototherapy at neonatal care units in Mosul City, Iraq. *Rawal Medical Journal*. 2023 May 27;48(2):379.-
22. Ahmed M M, Naji A B, Younis N M. Efficacy of an educational program based on health belief model to enhancing weight control behaviors among employees in the University of Mosul: a randomized controlled trial. *Revis Bionatura* 2023;8 (3) 28. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21931/RB/2023.08.03.28>
23. Younis NM. Evaluation the health lifestyle of kindergarten students at Mosul city/Iraq. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology & Legal Medicine*. 2023;26(1and2):148-52.
24. Bura'a LN, Younis NM. An Interventional Program on Nurses Knowledge and Practice towards Phototherapy in Neonatal Care Units. *International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology*. 2023 Jul 2;10(2):1428-32.
25. Younis NM, Taher AK. Efficacy of Trans Theoretical Model Intervention for Improving Behaviors related to Electronic Hookah Smoking among Healthcare Workers in Mosul Hospital: A Randomized Control Trail. *International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology*. 2023 Jul 2;10(2):1433-9.
26. Younis NM. Epidemiology of Hepatitis B-virus in Nineveh province: Retrospective Study. *International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology*. 2023 Jul 2;10(2):1440-4.

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27. Younis NM. Prevalence of Electronic Hookah and Risk Factors among University Students in Mosul City/Iraq. *International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology*. 2023 Jul 2;10(2):1422-7.
28. Ayed AY, Younis NM, Ahmed MM. Comparison of infection severity of vaccinated and unvaccinated health workers with Corona Virus: A cohort study. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*. 2023 Sep 1(1):336.
29. Younis N. M., Ahmed M. M., Ayed A. Y. HIV knowledge and preventive Standards Precautions Among Healthcare Workers in Blood Transfusion Centers. *Revis Bionatura* 2024; 9 (1) 44. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21931/RB/2024.09.01.44>
30. Younis NM, Ahmed MM, Dhahir NM. Knowledge and Attitude toward older adults among Nursing Students.2021.P J M H S Vol. 15, NO. 3,pp:683_685.
31. Abbas AS, Younis NM. Assessing the effect Pender's Model in changing employees' Eating Behaviors suffer hypertension at Mosul University Iraq. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2022 Jul 29;16(06):476.-
32. Hussein AA, Younis NM, Ahmed MM. Health Promoting Lifestyle profile Among Nursing Students in Mosul University. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*. 2020;24(09.(
33. Younis NM, Naji AB. Assessing the effect of an educational intervention based on health belief model on preventive behaviors of addiction. *Pakistan J Med Health Sci*. 2021;15(3):813-7.
34. Younis NM, Naji AB. Evaluation of preventive behaviors of addiction among students: Application of health belief model. *Indian J Forensic Med Toxicol*. 2021 May 17;15(4):1273-8.
35. Younis NM, Naji AB. The effect of health education based on the health belief model about changing the belief related to substance use among university students in Mosul city-Iraq. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*. 2021 May 4:14687-98.
36. Younis NM, Hussein AA, Ahmed MM, Younis NM. Quality of life and occupational hazards among cement factory workers in Mosul city. *QoL and Occupational Hazards among Cement Factory Workers*. 2021;24(2):1-8.
37. Younis NM. Assessment for Mortality Rate Children Under Five Years in Mosul City. *Journal of Kufa for Nursing Science* Vol. 2014;4(1.(
38. Younis NM, Naji A. Efficacy of Health Belief Model-Based Training in Changing the Beliefs about Substance use. *Kufa Journal for Nursing Sciences*. 2021 Jun 25;11(1):221-9.
39. Ahmed MM, Younis NM, Hussein AA. Association between Internet Addiction and Sleep disturbance Among Nursing Students. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*. 2020;24(09).
40. Bura'a LN, Younis NM. Educational Program of Nurses Practices Towards to Phototherapy at Neonatal Care Units. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023 Jun 9;17(04):530.-
41. Suleiman AA, Abed SM, Ahmed SS. Assessment the Levels of Depression among Patients with Hemodialysis at the Dialysis Centers in Mosul City. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023;17(08):67.-
42. Abed SM, Suleiman AA, Ahmed SS, Younis NM, Ahmed MM. Road Traffic Accident Characteristics And Injury Outcomes Among Victims In Mosul City. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*. 2023 Sep 15:4102-8.
43. Saad WI, Kumait AS, Younis NM. Workplace challenges and violence against nurses: subject review. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023 Mar 2;17(01):509.-
44. Taher AK, Younis NM. Evaluation Of Processes Of Change Related To Trans Theoretical Model Of Enhancing Behaviors Of Healthcare Workers User Electronic Hookah. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*. 2023 Mar 16:3190-3.
45. Alkaisy MS, Ahmed SS, Alsydan MS, Suleiman AA, Younis NM, Ahmed MM. Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Following Wars and Repression at Mosul City-Iraq. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*. 2021 May 17;15(3):1240-5.
46. Younis NM, Ali MT, Hasan MK, Khalaf MS, Abdullah MN, Ahmed YL, Abdulkadir MN. Knowledge and attitude of collegians at university in Mosul towards the prevention and control of COVID-19. *Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation*. 2021:7975-8.
47. Younis NM. Nursing students' attitudes towards older adult people. *Zagazig Nursing Journal*. 2015 Jul 1;11(2):151-9.
48. Younis NM, Ahmed MM, Hussein AA. Epidemiology Of Deaths From Injuries In Nineveh Governorate (2008_2012). *kufa Journal for Nursing sciences*. 2014;4(2.(
49. Younis NM, Ahmed MM. Knowledge and Compliance with Standard Precautions among Nursing Students in Mosul University. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*. 2014 Jun 1;2(3):152-9.
50. Naji AB, Ahmed MM, Younis NM. Adherence the preventive measure against for covid-19among teachers at university of mosul. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology & Legal Medicine*. 2021;24(3and4):273-7.
51. Ahmed MM, Younis NM, Hussein AA. Prevalence of tobacco use among health care workers at primary

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- health care centers in Mosul City. *Pakistan Journal of Medical and Health Sciences*. 2021;15(1):421-4.
52. Younis NM, Ahmed MM, Dhahir NM. Prevalence of coronavirus among healthcare workers. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology & Legal Medicine*. 2021;24(1and2):267-70.
53. Ahmed MM, Younis NM, Hussein AA. Violence towards nurses staff at teaching hospitals in Mosul City. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*. 2020 Jul 30;14(3):2598-603.
54. Younis NM, Ahmed MM, Hussein AA. Nurses' knowledge, attitude and practice towards preparedness of disaster management in emergency of mosul teaching hospitals. *Medico-Legal Update*. 2020 Jul;20(3):775-9.
55. Younis NM, Mahmoud M, Ahmed A. University Students' Attitude Towards E-Learning. *Bahrain Medical Bulletin*. 2021;43(2):460-2.
56. Muwfaq YN, Ahmed MM, Abdulsalam RR. Assessing Quality of Life in Palliative Care. *Bahrain Medical Bulletin* 2021;43(3):594-6.
57. The International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery Releases. Global Statistics on Cosmetic Procedures. Caught at:
58. <http://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/the-international-society-of-aesthetic-plastic-surgery-releases-global-statistics-on-cosmetic-procedures-300108852.html>.2019.
59. Saadoon AA, Hasan RA, Alrikabi SK, Audiab HB. Is Plastic Surgery, for Whatever Case, Unethical?. *University of Thi-Qar Journal Of Medicine*. 2023;26(2):188-200.
60. Doheyan TA, Saad AA, Haidar AA, Fwzan HA, Askar JA, Malki FA, Alanzi OH, Alanazi MQ, Alanazi WQ, Alanazi JQ, Alanazi FG. Knowledge, attitude and practices concerning cosmetic surgery among female medical students at the University Hospital, King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *British Journal of Medicine and Medical Research*. 2016 Mar 5;14(4):1-0.
61. Panse N, Panse S, Kulkarni P, Dhongde R, Sahasrabudhe P. Awareness and perception of plastic surgery among healthcare professionals in Pune, India: do they really know what we do?. *Plastic surgery international*. 2012;2012.
62. Tam KP, Ng HK, Kim YH, Yeung VW, Cheung FY. Attitudes toward cosmetic surgery patients: the role of culture and social contact. *The Journal of social psychology*. 2012 Jul 1;152(4):458-79.